

Review of Problems Encountered in Therapies in Clinical and Health Psychology Specialization

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Abstract

The Clinical and Health Psychology Specialization Division covers a wide range of topics related to clinical psychology, health psychology, psychotherapy, counseling, rehabilitation psychology, neuropsychology, and all areas of psychological intervention in traditional clinical settings (public and private hospitals, clinics, services) . These settings include both traditional clinical settings and innovative clinical settings. An important achievement of the biopsychosocial approach in the modern era of clinical and research activities in health is the link between medicine and psychology in the multidisciplinary and integrated treatment of the main organic and mental diseases. ("New and Old Adventures of Clinical Health Psychology in the Twenty ...") ("New and Old Adventures of Clinical Health Psychology in the Twenty ...") This connection is an integral part of the biopsychosocial approach. Contribution to this section is requested for articles in psychocardiology, behavioral medicine, psycho-oncology, psychogeriatrics, pain management, healthy lifestyle programs (such as weight loss programmes), neuropsychological rehabilitation, and other medical fields where psychology is significantly available. I encourage clinical trials, observational studies, research articles, reviews, meta-analyses, perspective and opinion articles, brief reports on evidence-based practice in clinical and health psychology, as well as the

presentation of empirically supported psychological treatments. supply a more robust scientific perspective on the applications of psychology in healthcare settings. The primary purpose of this article is to examine current issues and important concerns that have not been satisfactorily resolved in clinical health psychology-psychotherapy, as well as to suggest new and old research areas that can be published in this journal section. These are issues that still need to be addressed in the twenty-first century about clinical psychology and psychotherapy. The field of clinical psychology faces significant obstacles in the twenty-first century. The minimal impact of our discipline is a current critical issue. While the number of individuals receiving only psychotherapy is decreasing (Olfson & Marcus, 2010)" (Levin & Potts, 2016, p. 69), a negative fact is the negativity of psychotherapy.

Keywords: *Clinical Psychology, Health Psychology, Health Psychology Specialization, Clinical Psychology Specialization, Problems Encountered in Therapies*

1. Introduction

empirically supported therapies (ESTs) by physicians are not as widespread as it might be (Foa et al, 2013; Lilienfeld et al, 2013). Foa emphasized that the limited adoption of ESTs by practitioners and experts is a sign that fewer people are seeking therapy (Kessler et al., 2005). Although this problem has serious repercussions for the health and safety of patients, it has not been generally accepted that some treatments may be dangerous for patients (Lilienfeld, 2007).

According to a recent systematic review and meta-analysis of psychiatry, psychiatric treatments, and psychotherapy, at the turn of the 21st century it was emphasized that "people need to be listened to by someone (quite legitimate). So, the reason psychologists and psychotherapists are preferred over psychiatrists in some situations is that, in the public eye, psychologists and psychotherapists are more prepared to provide patients with an opportunity to talk about their problems (Holzinger et al., 2010; Moro et al., in press). (Angermeyer et al., 2017). To increase psychiatry's public reputation, the authors recommended less emphasis on prescription drugs and more emphasis on skills characteristic of clinical psychology, such as interactive and empathetic communication (Maj, 2014). When asked, patients "generally stated that they would rather receive psychotherapy or counseling to treat mental health problems than be prescribed psychotropic

drugs” (McHugh et al. 2013). This is true, although many patients have traditionally been invited to consider treatment based on the biomedical model of mental illness (p. 35, Gaudiano et al. 2016).

Moreover, despite decades of research, we still do not know enough about the processes of change and the active ingredients of much evidence-based therapies (Longmore and Worrell, 2007). As a result, there has been a significant cut in the budget distributed to the research and development of psychological treatments (Gaudiano & Miller, 2013). The use of an evidence-based strategy alone is insufficient to justify psychological therapies . Fortunately, the field of evidence-based psychological treatments, particularly cognitive-behavioral therapy , has made considerable progress over the past four decades (CBT; Layard & Clark, 2014a; p. 1). The recovery rate for patients with clinical depression or persistent anxiety disorder has been found to be as high as fifty percent, and many others show significant signs of improvement. The chance of recurrence was also roughly halved; therefore, cognitive behavioral therapy seems to be more beneficial than drug therapy in this regard. In addition, most patients choose cognitive behavioral therapy over drug therapy (McHugh et al. 2013).

2. Specific Examination, Identification and Classification of Specific Treatments

highlighted "the specific study, identification and classification of specific treatments for generally accepted psychopathologies that have been shown to be effective in experimental settings ". (“New and Old Adventures of Clinical Health Psychology in the Twenty ..”) The effectiveness of psychotherapy is "specifically examining, identifying, and classifying specific treatments for generally recognized psychopathologies that have been shown to be effective in experimental settings ." Paul asked, "What therapy , administered by whom and under what circumstances, is most successful for this person who is experiencing this exact problem?" It is especially important to answer the question. (Paul, 1967, p.111).

"Scientists were deliberately hiding a large number of important results because of an unreasonable adherence to a small set of scientific methodologies ," the researcher added. Indeed, it is normal to conclude that they can use strategies and define psychotherapy and research-based practice in ways that prevent therapists from being as successful as possible (Beutler, 1998). On the other

hand, most clinical psychologists and psychotherapists are reluctant to measure the impact of their therapeutic work (Castelnuovo et al., 2016d).

Persistent reliance on psychopharmacological therapies versus psychological interventions has been questioned by several psychiatrists (Moncrieff, 2006; Moncrieff & Cohen, 2006). For example, antidepressants are hypothesized to function on the unique neurobiology of depressive disorders, by a disease-centered pharmacological model of action. However, antidepressants often cause abnormal brain conditions that are not always associated with treatment. However, there is not much data to support this theory. The drug-centered alternative paradigm proposes that psychotropic drugs inadvertently produce abnormal states that can improve symptoms. Antidepressants can have a wide variety of drug-related effects, depending on the chemical class of the drug. These effects can range from lethargy and cognitive impairment to moderate excitement and even outright agitation . Both drug- related effects and placebo amplification may manage findings from clinical trials . There is no evidence to suggest that antidepressants or any other medication produce a long-term improvement in mood or other effects that are particularly effective in treating depression (Moncrieff and Cohen, 2006).

There is great hope that in the next few years this specialty will become a functional platform where researchers and clinicians can discuss empirical findings, views, theories and methodologies related to clinical health psychology.

3. Integration of Psychological Treatments Including Psychotherapy and Psychiatric Drugs

Due to the large body of evidence about the efficacy of combination therapy over pharmacotherapy or psychotherapy alone, future research needs to shift the direction from an old rationale that emphasizes the contrast between pharmacological treatments and psychological treatments to an integrative approach. The state of depression is a good example to consider when considering this (Guidi et al. 2011, 2016; Cox et al ., 2014; Cuijpers et al., 2014; Weitz et al., 2015, 2017). Further research is needed to decide the most effective combination or sequential approach to psychotherapy and pharmacology for each type of psychopathology and for each patient (Guidi et al. 2016). In this study, patients' preferences should also be considered (Angermeyer et al. 2017).

4. to focus your attention on the field of positive psychology

Both positive psychology and positive psychotherapy are interesting new modalities in the field of mental health care, and added research is needed not only in the field of Positive Psychology and Positive Psychotherapy of the *Frontiers* journal, but also in the Clinical and Health Psychology section (Schrack et al. 2014; Huber, et al. 2016).

Specifically, in the follow-up phase of treatment (Castelnuovo et al., 2016c) or in rural populations with limited access to healthcare, the use of healthcare platforms and modern technologies can help clinicians ensure continuity of healthcare aid after a traditional treatment. In some critical situations, this can help clinicians ensure continuity of health care after a traditional period of inpatient care. This needs to prove its usefulness and further work is needed, particularly in cost effectiveness, an industry where modern technologies can play a special role in the incremental maintenance approach (Castelnuovo and Simpson, 2011; Castelnuovo et al., 2015b, 2016d).

Specific and idiosyncratic psychological model built on the biopsychosocial framework (Engel, 1977, 1997) and must consider that the evidence-based approach must be balanced. (“New and Old Adventures of Clinical Health Psychology in the Twenty ...”) (Kahn, 2008; Castelnuovo, 2013), using the forgotten but still functional principles of Hippocrates in both traditional contexts and innovative (technology and internet-based) (Mantovani et al. 2003; Castelnuovo and Simpson, 2011; Manzoni et al., 2011) ; Castelnuovo et al., 2014, 2015a,b, 2016c) furthered their work.

5. Cognitive and Behavioral Principles-Based Therapy

Cognitive-behavioral therapy , sometimes also known as CBT, is a type of psychotherapy in which a therapist explores the connection between a patient's actions and ideas, feelings, or both. A CBT therapist will collaborate with a client to find unhealthy thought patterns and then try to change those habits. The therapist will talk to the individual about how these patterns can be created or cause already self-destructive actions and beliefs. The client and therapist can work together to create healthier ways of thinking about the problems they are facing. These adjustments can help a person adopt healthier, more optimistic attitudes as well as change their habits and beliefs.

According to the findings of the National Alliance for Mental Health (NAMI), cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) is an effective treatment for several diseases, including:

- anxiety disorders
- depression
- bipolar disorder
- eating disorders
- schizophrenia trauma -related disorders

6. Psychodynamic Therapy

Psychodynamic therapy is to aid individuals in overcoming destructive behavior patterns rooted in the individual's past. When taking part in this type of therapy, a person is encouraged to speak freely in response to questions posed by a therapist . This gives the therapist an opportunity to recognize repetitive patterns of behavior and cognition. A person can learn to overcome unhelpful habits and emotions if they understand how their experiences lead to the formation of such behaviors and emotions. According to an article published in 2018, psychodynamic therapy is effective in treating anxious disorders, borderline personality disorder (BPD), and depressive disorders. On the other hand, therapists use this approach to treat a wide variety of mental health-related conditions as well as personality issues. The level of intensity of psychoanalysis is higher than that of psychodynamic therapy. The American Psychiatric Association recommends that treatment sessions occur at least three times a week but can be more frequent if needed.

7. Treatment Involving the Use of Animals

In animal assisted therapy, the person spends time with a pet that has been trained to be a therapy animal. Anxiety and PTSD sufferers can receive help from the companionship of a therapy animal , which can help relieve their symptoms . There are some nursing homes, hospitals and other medical institutions that use therapy animals to supply support or comfort to patients . According to NAMI, people with cancer, cardiovascular disease or mental health issues can benefit greatly from working with therapy dogs. In a study in *Frontiers in Psychology*, researchers advocate using

animal-assisted therapy, along with music therapy, an enriched environment, and other supportive therapies, to reduce stress and trauma for hospitalized people who may need to be forced into hospitalization or isolation .

8. Emotion-Focused Counseling

The primary goals of emotion-focused therapy, commonly known as EFT, are to increase awareness of one's emotions and learn how to control and overcome those emotions. The Emotional Freedom Technique (EFT) encourages individuals to work with emotions rather than suppress them :

- depression \ layer
- I suffer from social anxiety.
- interpersonal difficulties
- problems in relationships caused by eating disorders

9. Counseling for Families

Primary focus of family therapy is the purpose of working with a family as a unit to aid a person in the family in solving specific challenges . Family therapists aid families in recognizing and breaking dysfunctional patterns of communication and interaction that may be the source of their difficulties. Family counseling can help households that include teenagers struggling with mental health issues, according to information presented in an article published in the International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health Trusted Source.

In addition, this type of treatment can help patients:

- drug abuse disorders
- eating disorders behavior problems
- anxiety
- OCD medical issues

People dealing with similar problems can take part in group therapy together to find solutions. Individuals in group therapy are given the opportunity to comment on the conversation or present their own personal views and experiences. The discussion is moderated by a therapist . By using group therapy , one can realize that one is not alone and gives participants a chance to support each other. However, one of the disadvantages of group therapy is that if the individual receives counseling individually, they may not receive as much individual attention as they would in a setting. Group therapy is also less confidential, which means that some people may hesitate to discuss their experiences with their peers. According to the American Group Psychotherapy Association, group therapy can help people who struggle with:

- concerns about interpersonal relationships
- Concerns about behavior, learning, or family life in children and adolescents
- Medical Issues
- aging problems
- symptoms include hopelessness, anxiety, and trouble recovering from a loss or tragedy.
- lifestyle issues
- dependence
- personality disorders

The act of training one's attention to focus on the here and now is known as mindfulness practice. Mindfulness practice aims to teach people to pay attention to and accept experiences and circumstances without judgment. Trusted Source discovered that mindfulness-based therapy helps reduce anxiety and depression in people with cancer. But experts hint that the effects of the treatment may not be long-lasting. Mindfulness training often includes meditation as a vital part.

Creative art therapy approach is to stimulate the mind through various artistic approaches. People taking part in creative art therapy are given the opportunity to express how they are feeling right now through a variety of genres, including painting, dance, music, and poetry. Play therapy is a type of therapy used by experts to encourage children to discuss their feelings and ideas . Play therapists supply an environment where children feel safe and cared for. Children in play therapy

can reveal their thoughts or experiences through how they play. A teen struggling with behavior issues, stress or trauma can work on these issues in the sheltered setting of this type of treatment.

The cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) approach is based on the premise that the thoughts and ideas you have about yourself, and the circumstances of your life can be a source of emotional pain. This condition may be a contributing factor to mental health problems, occur at the same time as other mental health problems, or develop because of other mental health problems. Like behavioral therapy, CBT does not spend a lot of time focusing on earlier events. Emphasis is placed instead on treating existing symptoms and making necessary corrections. For example, between therapy sessions you can start a notebook where you record useless ideas and things that bother you. This exercise helps reinforce what you learned in therapy and allows you to apply your new skills to everyday situations.

10. One of the Most Common Beliefs in Psychotherapy

One of the most common beliefs in the field of psychotherapy is that a healthy therapeutic alliance is the most crucial factor in deciding whether psychotherapy is effective (Wampold, 2015). The link is assumed to be more important than the underlying model of causality and changing its causal factors and is the universal process of change that unifies all different psychotherapy treatments. This method of thinking assumes that the creation of expectations through descriptions of the situation and relevant therapy, as well as the implementation of health-promoting activities, are common added variables (Lebowski et al., 2002). Cuijpers said there is potential to reduce the number of therapies available, given that meta-analyses have shown that a wide variety of psychotherapy treatments for depression are equally effective (Cuijpers, 1998). On the other hand, the findings of meta-analyses reveal the existence of variations between psychotherapies (Budd & Hughes, 2009; Tolin, 2010).

A meta-analysis of the relationship between therapeutic alliance and treatment outcome in eating disorders found that the relationship between alliance and outcome was weaker than that between early symptom relief and later alliance. This was the case, although the patient-rated quality of the therapeutic alliance was a good predictor of outcome in therapy (Cameron et al, 2018). (Graves et al., 2017). Thus, an improvement in early symptoms appears to have an impact on the later alliance.

It is also possible that the most successful therapies are those that result in the strongest relationships. What is missing are experimental studies that actively manipulate the therapeutic alliance, and as a result, the evidence stays limited to longitudinal predictive analyzes that may do little more than imply causal relationships. What is missing are studies that actively manipulate the therapeutic alliance (Fluckiger et al., 2018). The common assumption is that a well-working alliance is "something" found in interpersonal harmony between two people, providing the patient with a healing experience that appears to be part of a stable, benign relationship. (“Frontiers | Innovation in Psychotherapy, Challenges, and Opportunities ...”) This is the case, although there is no empirical evidence to support this theory. (“Netizen Report: Preventing bias or protecting extremism ... - Global Voices”) Associated with this concept is the assumption that some therapists have, and others do not; this translates into the assumption that there are diverse types of therapists, such as excellent and terrible . Unfortunately, this explanation does not meet the alternative but understudied notion that a healthy therapeutic relationship is an emerging phenomenon created by professionalism, realistic models, and the experience of change that begins exceedingly early in the therapeutic process.

In line with the hypothesis that alliance is in fact an emerging aspect of successful therapy, the therapeutic alliance that can be achieved with the use of the internet alone is surprisingly excellent (Heim et al., 2018). Persistent feeling of the therapeutic relationship as the primary factor underlying psychotherapy effectiveness is a barrier, as it reduces the need to develop innovative theories and techniques, which is a barrier. This feeling is a hindrance because it means that new techniques make only a marginal difference. Assigning the therapeutic relationship to the role of the critical cause of change rather than modeling it as an emerging phenomenon of change creates inertia in research on psychopathological mechanisms and peace of mind in therapists. (“Innovation in Psychotherapy, Challenges, and Opportunities: An Opinion ...”)

Often, new methods have been developed based on treatment techniques, more specifically , the creation of combinations of treatment methods that seem effective. Such strategies often have only a shaky foundation in theoretical models, and models of therapy processes can only be developed after the therapies themselves have been tried.

Technology design using a top-down approach begins with an overview of the system involved (for example, dysfunctional beliefs) but does not describe subsystems in sufficient depth or explain

how they affect functionality. For example, the cognitive model proposes that negative automatic thoughts and ideas manage either the onset or persistence of the disorder. However, as Wells and Matthews (Wells and Matthews, 1996) point out, this approach does not consider broader aspects of cognition that are known to be associated with the disorder, such as biases in the regulation of attention and control levels of the brain. Wells and Matthews also point out that this approach does not consider broader aspects of cognition that are known to be associated with the disorder. (“Innovation in Psychotherapy, Challenges, and Opportunities: An Opinion ...”) Because the cognitive-behavioral model has not kept pace with contemporary discoveries in cognitive psychology and philosophy, the clinical application of cognitive behavioral therapy is only tangentially related to knowledge of the underlying processes. Beck founded cognitive behavioral therapy on the depiction of cognitive distortion processes as well as the problematic thought content of patients (Beck, 1963, 1964). The main intervention developed from this observational technique consisted of using Socratic discussion to correct cognitive distortions and deficiencies in schema content. This fundamental change approach of cognitive therapy (IT) is taken from philosophy and is not grounded or supported by experimental psychology. Rather, IT is based on philosophical ideas. On the other hand, studies show that trying to replace dysfunctional thinking with more proper thinking can lead to thought suppression and negative paradoxical results (Longmore & Worrell, 2007; Magee et al., 2012). Later, behavioral activation, assertiveness training, anxiety management, or other strategies used for the first time in mindfulness meditation were combined to produce a more eclectic cognitive behavioral therapy . This was conducted by combining CBT with other modalities (CBT).

11. Dialectical Behavior Therapy

Dialectical behavior therapy is an added prominent example of a field's technique-driven evolution (DBT). It works on the premise that people diagnosed with borderline personality disorder lack the abilities needed to regulate their emotions (Linehan et al., 1991 ; Linehan, 2014). There are around fifty different skills taught to patients to increase their ability to regulate their emotions, and these skills form the basis of therapies . Once again, learning theory is used as a guiding principle in the choice of these abilities; however, none of these have been derived from

experimental psychology and have not been individually evaluated. Both cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) (Beck and Dozois, 2011) and dialectical behavioral therapy (DBT) (Stoffers et al., 2012) can be considered well supported by the evidence when viewed as whole packages. Part analysis has been used in several studies to show that primary and core technique may not be the key part when it comes to challenging considerations for content-level cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) (Jacobson et al., 1996). These studies were conducted to evaluate this hypothesis. An important advance in the field of psychotherapy was the introduction of disorder-specific treatment modalities for conditions such as depression, anxiety disorders, and personality disorders in the 1960s . These new methodologies have led to a significant expansion of psychotherapy activity for people who have been historically neglected despite serious illnesses.

Even if there is evidence that these treatments are innovative and have the potential to help, it is important to ask whether the technique-based strategy of mixing a variety of different procedures is the most effective way to develop new treatments. For example, therapy packages that have many components and are very eclectic may mask the potentially negative effects of constituent parts of individual treatment modalities (Castonguay et al., 1996). In summary, the examples above show that the technique-oriented approach common in psychotherapy (as in other professions) can be beneficial but can also lead to significant disadvantages.

12. Opportunities Starting with Basic Science

Contemporary behavior therapy refers to either general learning theory (including constructivism, cognitivism, and social cognitive theory) or information processing theory. Only two refer to a specific psychological theory taken from general psychology: metacognitive therapy (MCT) (Wells, 2009) develops and develops the concept of metacognition as presented by Flavell (Flavell, 1979). The self-regulatory executive function (S-REF) model, a comprehensive information processing model of human cognitive and emotional regulation, serves as its theoretical foundation (Wells & Matthews, 1996). Relational framework theory (RFT) is what is meant when people talk about acceptance and commitment therapy (ACT) (Hayes et al., 2001). The precise nature of the interaction that takes place between the approaches offered by RFT and ACT is still a matter of debate. For more detailed information, go here (see Zettle et al., 2016). Orienting treatment procedures to psychological systems or processes rather than mental illness, which are broad ideas

that summarize symptom clusters, is an important part of starting from the basic sciences. A reductionist approach is something that should inevitably appear from focusing on a particular process. For example, the MCT hypothesizes that worrying, rumination, and monitoring for potential threats are all components of the cognitive attention syndrome (CAS), an essential psychological process and a factor found in most illnesses. Focusing on worry, rumination, and attention to danger suggests that psychological dysfunctions such as anxiety are the result of this mechanism. However, if a strategy can restrict the CAS, then there is no need to directly treat the feeling of anxiety.

The MCT appears to be quite unique in that it only develops and uses methods that can be linked to parental theory, and that it was developed through a methodical evaluation of the assumptions derived from that theory. Case studies were used to prove the effects of manipulating the focus of attention using the attention training technique (ATT) at the onset of MCT to increase cognitive control and disrupt CAS (Wells, 1990). Later, studies were conducted showing the effects of attention enhancement on exposure (Wells and Papageorgiou, 1998). There is currently a large database supporting the possible effectiveness of ATT (Knowles et al., 2016; Fergus and Wheless, 2018) and complementing the MCT. [Knowles et al., 2016; Fergus and Wheless , 2018] (Normann et al., 2014). (“A Systematic Review of Efficacy of the Attention Training Technique in ...”) Although the behavioral therapy literature includes several methods designed to alter the focus of attention and attentional processes, these methods have generally focused on reducing anxiety through distraction rather than relying on a theory linking attention to psychological causal or maintenance mechanisms. The work in the field of attentional bias modification (ABM) offers an exception, based on the discovery that anxiety is associated with the "automatic processing" of threat-related information and that such bias can, in principle, be retrained. ABM stands for attentional bias modification (MacLeod, 2015). On the other hand, ATT and ABM examples like this seem to be among the very rare outliers in the field.

13. Conclusion and Recommendations

We see a change in basic assumptions in individual techniques such as MCT and ATT, with the development of therapeutic procedures mostly based on theory . This shift can be seen in the context of MCT and its individual techniques. In addition, the idea has a solid basis in empirical

attention-focused psychology research (Wells & Matthews, 1996). However, we need an awareness of the potential dangers associated with the creation of this treatment system and a continuing process of improving psychotherapy from a basic science point of view. Tools that can help include qualitative research investigating the impact of certain psychotherapy procedures, as well as case studies focusing on methods isolated from testing. It is possible that core principles of psychotherapy such as "doing a few things well" or "less is more" (low complexity leads to better skill acquisition, focusing on fundamentals leads to better decisions) show their advantages in further development. The practice of creating psychotherapy procedures from a foundation in basic research is the exception rather than the norm. On the other hand, this is not due to a lack of progress in general psychology. In fact, there is a significant amount of added information in this field that has obvious relevance waiting to be translated into psychotherapy techniques. For example, decision making (Morewedge & Kahneman, 2010), human collaboration (Rand & Nowak, 2013), heuristics (Raab & Gigerenzer, 2015), or structured emotion theory that needs to be translated (Barrett, 2017). The creation of the MCT supplies an example of a methodical approach to theory and testing that can be replicated in exploring the full potential of other psychological findings. This can be done by following the steps outlined in the earlier sentence.

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